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Bringing post-occupancy evaluation up front to enhance energy efficiency in residential buildings

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ABSTRACT

While previous research has shown the potential benefits of conducting post-occupancy evaluations (POE) to close operational performance gaps, ensuring residential buildings perform as designed still presents significant challenges. This study, through a systematic literature review, aims to address this challenge by investigating common methods and barriers to undertake POE in residential buildings, identifying the most common related performance gaps. Results showed the current static building industry with a lack of standardized practices and continuous data collection as the main barriers to undertake POE in residential buildings. Main performance gaps were related to lack of know-how, evidence-based decision-making, stakeholder engagement and user-centric approach. While data collection and building user engagement are often carried out during POE, considering them at the design phase and all through the implementation process plays a major role in achieving optimal building performance. Findings show that performance gaps are not only related to technical defects or occupant behaviour but also to decision-making and engagement practices at early phases. Ultimately, this study shows the need to change the current static, linear culture of design and implementation in residential building projects towards a dynamic, feedback-loop approach by proposing key considerations to address the most common performance gaps and promote more energy-efficiency residential buildings.

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Performance gap; BPE; POE; building user; residential building

Introduction

In light of the growing intensity of the climate crisis, reducing greenhouse gas emissions from the building sector by 80% from 1990 levels by 2050 is set as a key priority by the European Union (EU) (European Parliament, Council of the European Union, 2024). Considering that 85% of existing buildings will probably be in use by 2050 and that 72% were built before the 2000s (Gevorgian et al., 2021), it is essential to define design practices and retrofit strategies that help achieve highly energy-efficient residential buildings. In the attempt to facilitate this process, the technological advancements surrounding the retrofit industry have grown significantly as the ability to simulate building energy use; nevertheless, a persisting performance gap between predicted and actual building performance compromises the effectiveness of these interventions (Burman et al., 2014; Eon et al., 2020). The performance gap usually alludes to energy performance (Y. Bai et al., 2024; O’Hegarty et al., 2024; Zare et al., 2023). However, this is not only about energy but also about indoor air quality

(IEQ), daylight, building users’ satisfaction, return on investment, etc. (Brown & Gorgolewski, 2015; Orihuela & Orihuela, 2014; Sharmin & Khalid, 2022). Performance gaps can be divided into procurement gaps (when faults come from building design, construction process, system installation) and operational gaps (related to building users’ behaviour, system performance) (Burman et al., 2014). While it is standard to obtain the energy performance certificate (EPC) of a building before and after the intervention to (1) inform owners, buyers or renters about the energy performance of the building and potential costs and (2) support design decision-making, calculations are often based on standard occupancy assumptions and predicted energy consumption from energy simulations (Williamson et al., 2010). Furthermore, literature shows that the role of building users in the actual building energy performance is greater and more complex than can be currently ascertained through energy simulations alone (Elsayed et al., 2023). Assessing the impact of building users’ behaviour on the energy performance of a

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building is highly complex (Cuerda et al., 2019; Gupta & Kapsali, 2016), but building performance evaluations (BPE) and Post-Occupancy Evaluations (POE) have been shown to have potential to shed light on this complexity (Boissonneault & Peters, 2023; Elsayed et al., 2023). BPE and POE are both critical methodologies in the assessment of new, existing and refurbished domestic and non-domestic buildings, yet they differ fundamentally in their scope, objectives, temporal application, and methodological emphasis (Preiser et al., 2018a). BPE is defined as a systematic process of evaluating the performance of a building across the entire lifecycle (from design and construction to operation and even decommissioning), employing energy models, performance benchmarks, predictive analysis and user satisfaction (Preiser et al., 2018b). Constituting a distinct yet integral phase within BPE, POE specifically concerns the performance of a building after it has been occupied for a period of time, primarily aiming to gather systematic feedback from the building users regarding their experiences within the space (Zimring & Reizenstein, 1980). POE is meant to be inherently user-centred and diagnostic, often serving as a tool for identifying operational shortcomings concerning how the space supports its intended functions and informing future design improvements (Preiser et al., 2018b). While BPE provides a comprehensive assessment of the technical and environmental performance of the building, POE offers the opportunity to ensure that the building meets users' needs in real-world conditions (J. Zhao et al., 2024).

While POE as a term can be traced to the 1960s (P. Li, Froese, et al., 2018), relatively few POEs are still undertaken in residential building projects (Gonzalez-Caceres et al., 2019; Kasi & Kaliluthin, 2024; Leaman et al., 2010; Maslova & Burgess, 2023; Sodagar & Starkey, 2016). Oseland (2018) lists some of the erroneous perceptions of POE that may lead to their lack of popularity, including (1) only designers benefit from POE, (2) revealed mistakes damage the reputation of the designer, (3) it is only an additional step to a construction project that does not return any kind of financial benefits. Elsayed et al. (2023) also highlight the heterogeneity of methodologies employed in POE, and, therefore, divergence in data quality, attributed to the absence of a standardized evaluation framework. Furthermore, residential building projects' processes are still static as evidenced in the Finnish context by Tarpio et al. (2025), who illustrate that decision making still flows linearly downwards to architects who are placed as third or fourth in the chain of command, suggesting a construction and design process that does not encourage holistic communication between stakeholders,

particularly with those involved in the more technical stages of the project. It is therefore pivotal to understand the main barriers to design, implement and evaluate residential building projects, including retrofit interventions, that work in reality and how POE (characterized by its user-centred assessment process) can help support evidence-based decisions.

While papers discussing and conducting POE can be found (Altan et al., 2013; X. Bai et al., 2022; Breadsell & Morrison, 2020; Cuerda et al., 2019; Day, 2000; Gill et al., 2010; Glad, 2012; Gupta & Chandiwala, 2010; Gupta & Kapsali, 2016; Husin et al., 2018; Hussein & Uzunoglu, 2020; Ishiyaku et al., 2017; Kamruzzaman et al., 2024; Kowaltowski et al., 2006; Minami, 2007; Olanrewaju & Chong, 2021; Ortiz et al., 2023; Pannier et al., 2021; N. Pereira et al., 2016; Rogage et al., 2019; Uddin et al., 2023; Villa et al., 2023; Whang et al., 2024), it remains unclear, first, how to conduct POE in residential buildings systematically, and secondly how planning POE can help to not only identify performance gaps after the building has been occupied but support design and decisions to avoid unintended consequences early on in the design phase, i.e. closing the gap between predicted and actual building performance in reality. To shed light on this, this study conducted a systematic literature review on POE undertaken in residential building projects, analyzing common methods, barriers, and potential strategies to overcome them, consequently, identifying the most common related performance gaps. Ultimately, this study aims to provide a better understanding of the challenges and barriers faced in conducting POE in residential buildings, the most common causes of underperformance in residential buildings, and how planning POE at the design phase can help address the most common gaps between predicted and actual building performance. Furthermore, advancing existing research on POE and performance gaps in residential buildings, a dynamic, feedback-loop process is proposed along with key considerations to address the most common performance gaps found in the existing literature. The overarching research questions posed in this study are: what barriers and challenges to conduct POE exist in residential buildings? What are the most common causes of performance gaps? How can planning POE help address the most common performance gaps?

Methodology

To address the research questions above, the methodology defined in this study was structured into two phases: (1) systematic literature review to identify existing methods, challenges and strategies in POE as well as

Figure 1. Research methodology.

most common related performance gaps, and (2) qualitative content analysis for categorization and interconnections in order to define key considerations to address most common performance gaps in residential buildings, as graphically depicted in Figure 1.

A systematic review of peer-reviewed literature was conducted by following the methodology outlined by Xiao and Watson (2019), since it allows for the collection of evidence on specific questions, breakdown and digestion of existing knowledge, and synthesis of findings through a well-defined and transparent protocol (Gough et al., 2017). As graphically shown in Figure 2, the systematic review process involved three main steps: (1) searching for relevant articles based on the research plan; (2) applying inclusion and exclusion criteria to screen the sample; and (3) reviewing the final set of selected articles.

The focus for this systematic literature review was articles pertaining to POE in residential buildings with no restrictions regarding year of publication or country and published up to the end of 2024. Synonymous terms for apartment or house were used, and variations of the term POE were included (e.g. post-occupancy assessment) to include papers that use varied terminology. The search was conducted in Web of Science Core Collection database by using the fixed terms ‘*post-occupancy evaluation*’ OR ‘*POE*’ OR ‘*post-occupancy assessment*’ AND ‘*housing*’ OR ‘*residen**’ OR ‘*apartment**’ OR ‘*flat*’ NOT ‘*edgar*’ OR ‘*allen*’, resulting in 483 articles. The Web of Science Core Collection database was chosen as it ensures comprehensive coverage of peer-reviewed articles from a wide range of relevant publishers and databases (Birkle et al., 2020). Articles that were duplicates, behind paywall with inaccessible files, non-engineering or architecture subject areas, or written in a language other than English (this was the language of the research team) were removed ($n = 51$), and the final number of 432 articles was then imported into Zotero (Zotero, 2024). First, the 432 articles were assessed for eligibility based on title and abstract and those unrelated to building construction ($n = 174$) or

residential buildings ($n = 85$) were removed (Criterion 02 in Figure 2), resulting in 173 articles (see Figure 2, Step 03). Next, Zotero’s ‘Find Full Text’ function was used to automatically retrieve the articles in PDF-format, supplemented by the university library to acquire the articles that could not be retrieved automatically. After excluding inaccessible articles ($n = 27$), the final number of 146 articles was assessed for eligibility based on full-text reading (see Figure 2, Step 04). The final criterion 04 was applied to remove articles that did not include case study filed work ($n = 32$), did not focus on residential buildings ($n = 3$), or focused on urban planning ($n = 7$). The final sample of articles included in this study, after applying all the criteria above, consisted of 104 peer-reviewed articles, which were then imported to ATLAS.ti (ATLAS.Ti, 2024), an intuitive code-based tool for qualitative content analysis that enables deep understanding of the research findings.

To categorize and identify interconnections between methods, stakeholder groups involved in POE, barriers and existing strategies to overcome them, a qualitative content analysis approach was used in this study as defined by Schreier (2012). This methodology provides a robust framework for the systematic analysis of large-scale datasets, enabling the categorization of information and the explanation of interrelations between the identified categories. Three main steps were followed during the qualitative content analysis: (1) two researchers conducted the analysis of the defined categories independently to ensure the validity of the analysis and avoid bias (Groat & Wang, 2002); (2) using ATLAS.ti (ATLAS.Ti, 2024), the literature was first thematically coded and analyzed, after which through a second round, the initial coding system was refined by merging similar codes and creating a two-level coding structure to clearly define and analysis the content; (3) through a collaboratively iterative deductive process, predefined categories and their interconnections were redefined, resulting in five main categories

Figure 2. Literature review strategy.

(Performance gap, Closing performance gap, POE barrier, Method, Stakeholder) (see Table 1).

Results and discussion

Most of the case studies included in the reviewed literature were in Europe ($n = 42$), followed by Asia ($n = 38$) (Chandel et al., 2016; Mustafa & Kudus, 2022; Sutantio

et al., 2022; Xu et al., 2013), North America ($n = 8$) (Kellogg & Cumbre-Gibbs, 2023; Saldaña-Márquez et al., 2018; Siu et al., 2025), South America ($n = 8$) (Liang Wong & Krüger, 2017; Tori et al., 2022), Africa ($n = 6$) (Ammar, 2012; Atanda & Olukoya, 2019), and Oceania ($n = 5$) (Australian Building Codes Board, 2022); full list of locations per case study is provided in Table A1. Reviewed studies were mainly focused on non-

Table 1. Codes and subcodes with definitions.

Code	Definition	Subcode	Definition
Performance Gap	Terms that refer to moments where building performance does not meet expectations, or factors that lead to this (Burman et al., 2014).	Building as source	Relating to the physical building or equipment, stemming from the planning, design, or construction phases (Burman et al., 2014).
		Occupant as source	Relating to occupant behaviour, stemming from occupation phase (Burman et al., 2014).
Closing performance gap	Measures undertaken to fix the unexpected inefficiencies, regardless of if they are done after the POE or if they should have been done at the design and construction phase (Gupta & Kapsali, 2016).	Post-occupancy	Interventions that are made after occupancy has begun (Gupta & Kapsali, 2016)
		Pre-occupancy	Interventions that should have been made at the planning, design, or construction phases (Vidal et al., 2020)
POE barrier	Challenges or obstacles to conducting good quality POE (Elsayed et al., 2023).	Barrier to any data	Factors that make POE initiation difficult, such as lack of funding or policy to incentivise building performance evaluations (Oseland, 2018).
		Barrier to good data	Factors that make the POE process difficult, and can lead to poor-quality data (Sebastian-Coleman, 2013).
		Barrier to data use	Factors that make the collected POE data difficult to analyze, disseminate, or incorporate in new projects (Maslova & Burgess, 2023).
Method	The physical instrument used to collect data, or methods that would directly produce new data (for example frequency of measurement, duration) (Elsayed et al., 2023).	Smart technologies	Physical devices that can collect and transmit information on building operation (Maslova & Burgess, 2023).
Stakeholder	An individual or group that was directly involved in POE (H. Li, Ng, et al., 2018).	Each stakeholder coded separately, for example owner, tenant, architect, municipality, engineer.	N/A

refurbishment buildings ($n = 93$), with only a few of them focusing on refurbished buildings ($n = 11$). Building types included apartments (Gonzalez-Caceres et al., 2019; Hassanain et al., 2024; Minami, 2007; Vidal et al., 2020), semi-detached housing (Breadsell et al., 2019; Breadsell & Morrison, 2020; Colclough & Salaris, 2024; Gupta & Chandiwala, 2010), and detached housing (Breadsell et al., 2019; Day, 2000; Gupta & Kapsali, 2016; Mlecnik et al., 2012; Rebaño-Edwards, 2007), where most occupants were not owners themselves (only 10 cases had owner-occupants among the participants) (Adekunle & Nikolopoulou, 2020; Altas & Ozsoy, 1998; Breadsell et al., 2019; Colclough & Salaris, 2024; Dabaieh et al., 2016; Gupta et al., 2014; Hendrickson & Wittman, 2010; Jenkins et al., 2010; Pretlove & Kade, 2016; Sharmin & Khalid, 2022). Regarding the stakeholders identified in the case studies, a recurrence-based list categorized by their role is provided in Table A2. Note that terms used to define stakeholders may differ amongst the reviewed studies due to professional and legal context-specific differences. While most case studies involved building users and owners in the project (Colclough et al., 2022; Hendrickson & Wittman, 2010; N. Pereira et al., 2016), only seven case studies collected building users' perceptions before the implementation of the project (Breadsell & Morrison, 2020; Dabaieh et al., 2016; Gupta & Chandiwala, 2010; Gupta & Gregg, 2016; Jenkins et al., 2010;

Sharmin & Khalid, 2022; Shirani et al., 2022), with one of them implementing a participatory design approach (Sharmin & Khalid, 2022). Questionnaires or surveys ($n = 79$) were the main method used for data collection from building users in the selected studies, followed by interviews ($n = 29$), in contrast to 12 studies where building users' experience was not considered at all (Altan et al., 2013; Altas & Ozsoy, 1998; Arriazu-Ramos et al., 2021; Colclough et al., 2018; Cuerda et al., 2019; Gill et al., 2011; McLeod & Swainson, 2017; P. Pereira et al., 2020). Professional stakeholders (i.e. architects, engineers, managers, etc.) rarely interacted with each other during the project implementation and involvement was in silos at specific phases of the project implementation (Pannier et al., 2021). Qualitative data collection methods used in the reviewed literature included interviews, questionnaire (often using 5-point Likert scales) (Husin et al., 2012), focus groups (Gupta & Chandiwala, 2010), expert evaluations (Glad, 2012), walkthrough (Agyefi-Mensah et al., 2020), photographic and video surveys (Dabaieh et al., 2016), and binary scale questionnaire (Sharmin & Khalid, 2022). Quantitative methods included real-time occupant location (Spataru & Gillott, 2011), benchmark criteria (Setiadi et al., 2020), energy simulations (Guerra-Santin et al., 2016; Rohdin et al., 2014; Xue et al., 2016), and indoor environmental quality through data loggers (Aguilar-Perez et al., 2023). It is important

to note that quantitative data was often collected only at one or two points in time (Brown, 2016; Gonzalez-Caceres et al., 2019; Maachi et al., 2019; Martínez & Kelly, 2019; N. Pereira et al., 2016; Rohdin et al., 2014), and hardly ever continuously throughout longer periods such as a year or more (Berge & Mathisen, 2016; Colclough et al., 2018, 2022; Colclough & Salaris, 2024; Cuerda et al., 2019; Gill et al., 2010, 2011; Gupta & Gregg, 2016; Gupta & Kapsali, 2016; Ortiz et al., 2023; Pannier et al., 2021; Patlakas et al., 2014; Pretlove & Kade, 2016; Rodríguez-Vidal et al., 2024; Sodagar & Starkey, 2016; Vidal et al., 2020; Williamson et al., 2010); data collection methods per case study are listed in Table A3.

Challenges for conducting POE in residential buildings

POE has been shown to be a useful tool to identify operational performance gaps (Colclough et al., 2022; Gupta & Kapsali, 2016; Mlecnik et al., 2012; Pretlove & Kade, 2016). However, conducting POE to assess if the building performs as designed is not a common practice, and if conducted, the process is still linear without opportunities to address performance gaps caused in the design phase (Hendrickson & Wittman, 2010; Kowaltowski et al., 2006; Mlecnik et al., 2012; Sharmin & Khalid, 2022). The reviewed literature showed that one of the main barriers to conduct POE tends to relate to the subjectivity surrounding qualitative data collection (Hendrickson & Wittman, 2010; Jenkins et al., 2010). For example, occupants may report having good control over their thermal environment, despite the fact that they do not understand how to use the thermostat (Macintosh & Steerners, 2005) or, otherwise, they report no issues with thermal control devices in spite of having never interacted with them (Baborska-Narozny et al., 2014). Human experiences of indoor thermal comfort are difficult to measure, indirectly connected to previous living conditions (Woo, 2017) and gender differences (Razem et al., 2025; Uddin et al., 2023), as e.g. they may report low satisfaction level even though average measured temperatures are within acceptable limits (Adekunle & Nikolopoulou, 2016). Furthermore, residents often lack motivation to answer questionnaires or engage in interviews (Xue et al., 2016), making it difficult to conduct continuous engagement sessions during the occupancy period (Breadsell & Morrison, 2020; Maslova & Burgess, 2023).

Additionally, a lack of POE culture in the building industry (Gonzalez-Caceres et al., 2019; Husin et al., 2018) leads to time, resources, and staff to not be allocated at the onset of a project to carry out evaluations

after commissioning. Another common barrier in residential buildings is the ethical and logistical side of carrying out POE in private properties (Hendrickson & Wittman, 2010; Rogage et al., 2019) and difficulty in engaging the building users (Brown & Gorgolewski, 2015). Good quality data collection, mainly due to inconsistency in methods (Elsayed et al., 2023; H. Li et al., 2022), single-point data collection (Rogage et al., 2019), and subjectivity in questionnaire-based data (Macintosh & Steerners, 2005) were also found to be common challenges in POE in the reviewed literature. Whereas quantitative data collection is more often carried out, a combination of both qualitative and quantitative data is not a common practice (Elsayed et al., 2023; Maslova & Burgess, 2023; Sharmin & Khalid, 2022; Tweed & Zapata-Lancaster, 2018). Questionnaires are often limited in scope to serve stakeholders' needs rather than meaningfully improving understanding of building performance (Kim et al., 2024; Leaman et al., 2010), do not pay enough attention to design aspects (Sharmin & Khalid, 2022), nor to relevant contextual information of building users (Woo, 2017). When it comes to quantitative data collection, common challenges are related to inadequate sensor placements (Aguilar-Perez et al., 2023; Elsayed et al., 2023) and missing readings during the monitoring period (Aguilar-Perez et al., 2023), making it difficult to define ranges of comfortable temperatures (Vidal et al., 2020) and understand the interconnection between indoor thermal comfort and building users' perceptions (H. Li et al., 2022). If data is collected, the lack of open datasets (Tuniki et al., 2021) and the know-how to use it in future design (Brown, 2016; Way & Bordass, 2005) were also commonly highlighted in the included studies.

Common causes of performance gaps

Existing literature showed that all buildings where POE was conducted had problems with user satisfaction or energy performance, which could have been rectified at the design phases, such as design for effective cross ventilation and solar control (Vidal et al., 2020), greater control of indoor environment (H. Li et al., 2022), air exchange rate dimensioning (Mlecnik et al., 2012), HVAC system design (Mlecnik et al., 2012), occupant involvement and stakeholder engagement (Kamruzzaman et al., 2024; Khoo et al., 2022; Ortiz et al., 2023; Pannier et al., 2021; Sharmin & Khalid, 2022), or housing flexibility and generous shared spaces (Avilla-Royo et al., 2024). Results also showed that in many cases, performance gaps arise from building users' behaviour (Altan et al., 2013; Breadsell & Morrison, 2020; Glad, 2012; Gonzalez-Caceres et al., 2019; Mlecnik et al.,

2012; Pannier et al., 2021). Examples include a lack of understanding of how equipment works (Macintosh & Steerners, 2005), inappropriate use of ventilation systems (Macintosh & Steerners, 2005) and difficulties in contacting building managers when equipment needs maintenance (Hassanain et al., 2024). While it is not typical in non-refurbishment buildings to involve their future building users in the planning or design process (Dikmen & Elias-Ozkan, 2016; Guerra-Santin et al., 2016; Pannier et al., 2021; Sharmin & Khalid, 2022), in renovation projects, the end users are already known before the planning and design phases start, and therefore, the engagement of building users should be more feasible; however, it is not a common practice yet (Dikmen & Elias-Ozkan, 2016). Building projects often adhere to a static, linear culture where stakeholders manage their own tasks siloed and engagement between stakeholders from different disciplines is uncommon (Liu et al., 2019; Pannier et al., 2021). If feedback mechanisms exist, they are often limited to checkboxes and reporting matters (Rogage et al., 2019), lacking a comprehensive understanding of user feedback (Gupta & Chandiwala, 2010; Gupta & Kapsali, 2016; Mlecnik et al., 2012). Results also showed lack of communication and clarity regarding responsibilities during occupancy (Hassanain et al., 2024), e.g. who is responsible for conducting tasks related to maintenance and repair, highlighting the need to establish a stakeholder engagement strategy where (1) 'what will be done' and (2) 'by who' is clearly defined (McLeod & Swainson, 2017). Furthermore, a stakeholder engagement strategy can help align the goals or needs of the different parties involved in a project (Leaman et al., 2010), particularly the building users, reducing future costs stemming from poor understanding of equipment operation (Gupta & Kapsali, 2016), unnecessary interventions (Brown,

2016; Da Silva et al., 2020; Kowaltowski et al., 2006), inefficient commissioning, building performance, or building users' dissatisfaction (Berge & Mathisen, 2016; Colclough et al., 2022; Cuerda et al., 2019). Figure 3 graphically summarizes the most common performance gaps in the current static, linear process deployed in the residential building projects analyzed in this study. An estimate of the performance gap proportions related to each phase of the project development is provided, based on the reviewed literature, divided into procurement and operational gaps. The *planning* phase often centres on administrative tasks, where a lack of planning for building user engagement, collection of feedback and in-situ quantitative measurements to inform the design process and POE at the later stage can lead to a 16-45% performance gap related to technical issues (O'Hegarty et al., 2024; Zare et al., 2023). *Design* is the phase when decisions relating to physical construction and interventions are made, and if solely based on siloed assumptions, it can lead to twice or five-time higher energy consumption than expected (approximately 16-45% performance gap) (Alam et al., 2019; Y. Bai et al., 2024). *Construction* phase consists of the implementation of the decisions delineated in the planning and design phases. Common construction defects, inefficient quality management, lack of knowledge and skills, and delays can increase performance gaps up to 25-60% (Alencastro et al., 2019; Bros-Williamson et al., 2015; Eon et al., 2020). *Commissioning* is the phase where construction finishes, and occupancy can resume or begin. Technical performance of the building is often assessed, but lack of methods and best-practice protocols is not available for many inspectors or building owners (Elzarka Hazem, 2009; Mills, 2011). *Post-occupancy* refers to the state of the building once building users have been

Figure 3. Graphical summary of most common performance gaps in the current static, linear process in residential building projects based on the reviewed literature.

lived in for at least six months (Zimring & Reizenstein, 1980). While building users' behaviour can still be influenced at this phase, certain interventions are only made more effective if considered early in the planning and design phases.

Potential to reduce performance gaps in residential building projects

The reviewed literature showed that even well-designed and implemented residential building projects can underperform due to unpredictability of building users' behaviour, decisions made in silos, assumptions based on energy models in planning and design phases, or lack of performance tracking (post-intervention monitoring) (Asadian et al., 2023; Wei et al., 2024). However, analyzing the most common causes of performance gaps found in the reviewed literature, this study proposes a dynamic, feedback-loop process along with key considerations that could help address most common performance gaps considerably if adopted early in the planning and design phases. Figure 4 provides a comprehensive overview of the transition needed to address most common performance gaps, from the current static, linear process (at the top) to a more dynamic, feedback-loop process (at the bottom) where a user-centric approach is implemented early in the project to support the economic and technical development and implementation. Main considerations to

support this transition are also depicted across the different project phases.

Standard BPE protocols and culture often follow solely an economic and technical approach from planning to commissioning, where a user-centric approach is not implemented until POE (Sodagar & Starkey, 2016) (see Figure 3). Whereas energy-efficient building performance is often associated with technological aspects, building users' behaviour plays a major role in it as well (Colclough et al., 2018; Hendrickson & Wittman, 2010). Building users are not often familiar with technical matters related to the performance of HVAC systems, nor know who to contact in case of defects or need for maintenance (Hassanain et al., 2024). Greater involvement of building users in the design phase can help designers to better understand their needs (Gupta & Gregg, 2016), and building users to know how to use the equipment and facilities to achieve the expected performance (Guerra-Santin et al., 2016; Gupta & Chandiwala, 2010; Ortiz et al., 2023; Pannier et al., 2021). While the use of smart applications gives greater control of the indoor thermal environment, such as programmable smart thermostats (Baborska-Narozny et al., 2014), and consequently can help reduce HVAC-related performance gaps (Adekunle & Nikolopoulou, 2016; H. Li et al., 2022; Macintosh & Steerners, 2005), this requires an occupant-centric approach to ensure building users' acceptance (Sodagar & Starkey, 2016). Building user manuals (Baborska-Narozny et al., 2014),

Figure 4. Graphical overview of key considerations to address the most common performance gaps in residential building projects.

training sessions (Breadsell et al., 2019; Pannier et al., 2021) and clear maintenance protocols, such as how to carry out the cleaning of dust from HVAC inlets (Lee & Shepley, 2018; Macintosh & Steerners, 2005), can help reduce inefficiencies in equipment performance. Similarly, clarity in communication through, for example, easier to read energy bills (Altan et al., 2013; Mlecnik et al., 2012), visualization of environmental conditions (Patlakas et al., 2014), and feedback-loop sessions to communicate with design teams (Gupta & Chandiwala, 2010; Gupta & Kapsali, 2016; Husin et al., 2018; Zhong & Gou, 2023) would enhance the long-term performance of the building. Continuous building user engagement sessions (Brown & Gorgolewski, 2015; Gupta & Gregg, 2016) and home demonstration tours (Baborska-Narozny et al., 2014) during occupancy could help understand specific building users' needs (Orihuela & Orihuela, 2014) and address their individual ergonomic requirements (Oliveira & Elali, 2012). Another aspect highlighted from the results was that BPE are commonly conducted by using theoretical guidelines, standards and energy simulations, where empirical evidence (i.e. data on energy use, IEQ, building users' expectations) to support decision-making is missing (Elsayed et al., 2023; Tuniki et al., 2021; Vidal et al., 2020). It is therefore clear the need for more robust qualitative data collection methods such as ethnographic studies, elicitation studies, or brainstorming (Bavaresco et al., 2020) all along the implementation project (from design to commissioning).

Unique in its approach, this study proposes the adoption of a POE user-centric approach early in the planning phase, and continuously through the project implementation (see Figure 4, bottom side) to address most common performance gaps related to building users' behaviour (accounted for between 40-75%) (Cleverger Caroline et al., 2014). This means, as presented in Figure 4, the introduction of feedback loop, facilitating stakeholder engagement through the different project phases, collection of relevant quantitative data, and building users' experiences and needs (Glad, 2012; Gupta & Chandiwala, 2010) to support evidence-based decision-making (dos Santos et al., 2024). Some advances have been made in the right direction, however, a systematic transition from the current static, linear process towards more dynamic, feedback-loop project development processes is still needed to maximize building energy efficiency in reality. In Figure 4, a linear process (top side) represents traditional construction projects where there are no plans to return upon completion, whereas those following a more dynamic process (bottom side) implement a feedback

loop throughout the project development, facilitating stakeholder engagement and communication, including building users. Typical refurbishment projects in residential buildings often carry out BPE in the planning phase to design the retrofit intervention, mainly based on non-validated energy simulations, where building users are not involved, communication between different stakeholders during the project implementation is scarce, and POE to ensure the building performs as designed is not often conducted. Defining a stakeholder engagement plan, including building users (Gupta & Chandiwala, 2010) and professional stakeholders (Avilla-Royo et al., 2024; Sharmin & Khalid, 2022), through recurring meetings (Avilla-Royo et al., 2024) can facilitate a more open discussion and understanding at the planning phase, support BPE and decision-making in the design phase. Interaction and evaluation should continue throughout the design and construction phases, keeping all stakeholders and building users informed and creating opportunities for discussion. However, active recruitment of participants is recommended to avoid self-selection biases and ensure all building users' profiles are represented (Avilla-Royo et al., 2024). Considering building users' future needs and expectations in the design phase will also enable the provision of flexible living spaces (Avilla-Royo et al., 2024; Sharmin & Khalid, 2022). While energy simulations can help foresee potential energy-related performance gaps (Colclough & Salaris, 2024; Martínez & Kelly, 2019; Yu et al., 2019), energy models must be validated by using in-situ data collection. This requires the definition of a systematic and robust one-year long pre-intervention qualitative (Breadsell & Morrison, 2020; Guerra-Santin et al., 2016) and quantitative data collection (Guerra-Santin et al., 2016; Gupta & Chandiwala, 2010). A collection of a wide variety of data, e.g. energy, CO₂, temperature, mean radiant temperature, relative humidity, movement detection, energy metering, and lux levels across seasons (Guerra-Santin et al., 2016; Gupta & Chandiwala, 2010), supplemented by building users' behaviour monitoring and questionnaires (Breadsell & Morrison, 2020; Gupta & Chandiwala, 2010), allows triangulation analysis for more accurate performance gap analysis (Guerra-Santin et al., 2016). Another important action to consider in the design phase to reduce performance gaps consists of establishing a quality assurance plan where the project team defines actions, activities, tasks and responsibilities for the intervention and commissioning phases, ensuring the final solutions meet the predefined quality standard (Gupta & Chandiwala, 2010; Pretlove & Kade, 2016). This may follow with the development of extensive maintenance protocols where actions,

responsible person and communication channels are defined (Hassanain et al., 2024; Lee & Shepley, 2018; Rogage et al., 2019). However, communication needs to be made more thorough along the whole project implementation, including not only through surveys but also through feedback collection on building users' lived experiences (Breadsell & Morrison, 2020; Gupta & Chandiwala, 2010). During commissioning, technical inspections are conducted as defined in the quality assurance plan and building users are informed (and trained if needed) about the new built environment and equipment in on-site sessions by using comprehensive material such as physical user-friendly manuals (Gupta & Kapsali, 2016) or engagement material like video journals (Razem et al., 2025). Follow-up visits after commissioning (i.e. after six months, two years and five years (Avilla-Royo et al., 2024; Breadsell & Morrison, 2020)) to ensure the building is used as expected and to implement double-loop training sessions (Glad, 2012), if new technological solutions are implemented, can also reduce performance gaps related to building users' behaviour (Gupta & Gregg, 2016). Through feedback loops, and continuous data collection and communication with building users, the outcome and the process can be critically analyzed, further performance gaps found, mitigation measures defined, and future interventions improved.

Opportunities for future research and practical applications

While this study shows the complexity of reducing performance gaps in residential buildings due to the multiple range of factors affecting the actual performance of a building, key considerations to address the most common performance gaps in a systematic and effective way are proposed in Figure 4. Since the review was completed there have been several articles published in BRI (Almomeni et al., 2025; Boissonneault & Peters, 2025; Y. Zhao et al., 2025) that underpin the uniqueness of this study, which provides a comprehensive overview of main causes of performance gaps per project phases, not only focusing on energy but the overall indoor built environment and building users' behaviour, suggesting then practical considerations for practitioners. Furthermore, key insights for further research on causes of performance gaps in residential buildings, good practices to conduct BPE and POE for both practitioners and researchers involved in real-life projects, are discussed. It is important to note that the implementation of these findings will not eliminate procurement and operational performance gaps completely; however, the energy performance of buildings along with building

users' satisfaction could be improved considerably. Whereas the proposed considerations can support the implementation process of residential building projects towards reducing performance gaps, further research is needed to test, refine and complement the proposed application approach and actions in real contexts that are very different to those included in the systematic literature review, specifically those with different climatic, cultural and built environment characteristics. Regarding results, the authors acknowledge the limitations of using only one database and existing case studies from peer-review articles and therefore recommend future research where quantitative and qualitative data from real case studies may help strengthen the evidence base and assess the proposed key considerations to reduce performance gaps; however, this is outside the scope of this study. Furthermore, the authors acknowledge the complexity of implementing the proposed considerations in real case studies due to the multidimensional complex nature of residential building projects, which depends on a wide range of factors.

Regarding practical implications of this study, it can be highlighted that the development of simple guidelines in collaboration with relevant stakeholders involved in residential building projects towards a more unified strategy (Boissonneault & Peters, 2025). Moreover, new strategies for the engagement of stakeholders and building users should be developed and tested in real case studies to support the implementation process and address related performance gaps. For instance, guidelines on how to define a stakeholder engagement plan in (refurbished) residential building projects, including building users. Also, current BPE protocols should be refined by (1) integrating a feedback loop throughout the project implementation and (2) POE approaches in the earlier phases (planning and design), indicating POE actions, data and protocols needed to effectively conduct POE at the latest stage. This will facilitate thorough data collection during the project and optimal evaluation of building performance at the end of the intervention.

Conclusions

While there are innovative solutions to considerably improve building energy efficiency, ensuring buildings perform as designed after the intervention (i.e. closing performance gaps) still presents significant difficulties. This study, through a systematic literature review, investigates the common methods and barriers to undertake POE in residential buildings and identifies the most common related performance gaps, providing a comprehensive understanding of how to approach

residential building projects to reduce the gap between predicted and actual building performance.

Results showed that successful implementation of POE suffers from challenges in qualitative data collection (for example, lack of quality and building users' engagement) and inconsistency in methods and standards, meaning current methods and outcomes considerably differ from each other to benefit future interventions. Another common barrier in residential buildings showed in the reviewed literature is the ethical aspect of involving and accessing private housing, making the involvement of building users rather difficult or even impossible. Furthermore, results highlighted that POE is not a common practice in the current building industry culture, time or resources are not set aside for its deployment, quantitative and qualitative data before and after intervention is not commonly collected, and stakeholders do not engage with each other nor with building users throughout the implementation process. This means evaluations will lack well-rounded feedback from all stakeholders and building users, increasing the risk of performance gaps. While POE has been shown to help address operational performance gaps at the later phase of the project, it is already late to solve procurement gaps that originated during planning, design and/or implementation phases.

Analyzing the most common performance gaps found in the reviewed literature, unlike recent study on POE in residential buildings (Almomani et al., 2025; Y. Zhao et al., 2025), this study provides a deeper understanding about most common performance gaps in residential building, showing that they are not only related to technical defects or building users' behaviour (operational gaps) but also related to decision-making in planning and design phases, lack of knowledge, skills and communication between all the stakeholders (including building users) involved in the project (procurement gaps). Furthermore, the main causes of performance gaps were mapped across the project phases and clustered into procurement and operational gaps, providing practical considerations for addressing them. A key aspect to highlight from the results is the potential of bringing the user-centric approach of POE upfront (as shown in Figure 4) by defining a feedback-loop process where interaction between different stakeholders (including building users) is continuous through the project development.

The scope of this paper revealed noteworthy case studies from a wide range of countries and years, it is however limited to those published in English and accessible through the authors' institution. Articles published after the completion of the literature review were not included, and only peer-reviewed articles including

case studies were considered, i.e. excluding books and grey literature. While this study focuses on POE undertaken in residential buildings, key findings are also applicable to other building types when it comes to the implementation of a more dynamic, feedback-loop process in building projects. Findings from this study highlight that good stakeholder engagement and holistic evaluation processes in early planning and design phases can prevent, and even solve, main performance gap issues and improve the performance of the implemented solutions. Furthermore, the need for professionals and building users to meet and discuss regularly requires a transition from a linear model to a dynamic engagement process, i.e. the impact of building users' behaviour on the performance of the building need to be assessed (through POE) to ensure the building works or is being used as intended, and a maintenance plan needs to be put in place to guarantee the building performs as planned in the long term.

Ultimately, this study highlights the need to change the current static, linear culture of design and implementation in residential building projects towards a more dynamic, feedback-loop approach (from planning and design phases to POE) by proposing key considerations that can support this transition. Furthermore, the proposed considerations can support the deployment of optimal BPE in residential building projects to maximize its energy performance while ensuring building users' needs and expectations. Underpinned by the latest study conducted by Boissonneault and Peters (2025), the authors believe that this study may help academics advance existing research on residential building performance gaps, practitioners with the actual implementation, and decision-makers with the development of optimal methods and practices to promote energy efficiency in residential buildings.

Author contributions

CRedit: **Raúl Castaño-Rosa:** Conceptualization, Formal analysis, Funding acquisition, Methodology, Supervision, Validation, Visualization, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing; **Dara Nerweyi:** Formal analysis, Visualization, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing.

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Data availability statement

The authors confirm that data sharing is not applicable to this article as no new data were created or analyzed in this study.

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